

Strategic plan 2026-2028

Engagement & Inclusion focal area

May 2026

Universiteit
Leiden

Focal area coordinators

Carole de Bordes

Rodrigo Costas

Tjitske Holtrop

Vincent Traag

Focal area members

Anli, Zeynep

Amanatidis, Anestis

Bezuidenhout, Louise

Brasil, André

Calero Medina, Clara

Dudek, Jonathan

Franssen, Thomas

Ge, Huilin

Hessels, Laurens

Meijer, Ingeborg

Mulati, Biegzat

Noyons, Ed

Parrón Cabañero, Ana

Putri, Annida

Rafols, Ismael

Reyes Elizondo, Andrea

Tijssen, Robert

Varga, Judit

Wang, Dongyi

When, Uta

Williams, Rachel

Xie, Qianqian

Yegros, Alfredo

1. Introduction

This document presents the strategic plan for the CWTS Focal Area Engagement & Inclusion (FA E&I) for 2026–2028, summarising multiple rounds of discussion among FA members and coordinators. It introduces our overarching vision alongside strategic (long-term impacts) and operational objectives (aimed at realising these impacts).

This strategy document provides a roadmap for the FA’s development, guiding strategic decisions on future opportunities (e.g. projects, partnerships, infrastructures) and providing a framework to reflect on our evolution and direction. While open to updates, the strategy is intended to remain stable over the period 2026-2028, serving as a foundation for subsequent years, with our vision staying consistent, but with some flexibility in our strategic and operational objectives, thus making the strategy a guide for direction at FA E&I, but not a straitjacket.

2. Vision

Science is opening up, not only in Open Science or research assessment but also in the growing recognition of its diversity of skills, perspectives, and approaches, and its increasing engagement with society (e.g. industry, policymakers, or citizens). In some cases, societal stakeholders become involved in science through transdisciplinary research or citizen science. Yet there are still clear disparities in who participates in science, what topics are researched and how. Increased attention for transdisciplinarity and citizen science has not resulted in full alignment between scientific research and societal needs, with many pressing societal and environmental challenges still insufficiently addressed (e.g. understudied diseases, citizens' calls on health and environmental effects of industries or agriculture). At the same time, available research is not always effectively taken up by society, and it may even be contested, with evidence-informed policy-making remaining suboptimal amid the influence of think tanks, lobbies, and lack of scientific expert advice. This raises questions about public communication, engagement, and understanding of science.

Against this backdrop, we formulate the overall vision for the FA E&I as:

Foster diverse and inclusive knowledge systems that engage with societal needs and challenges.

Our vision captures two core elements: the diversity and inclusion of knowledge systems, and the role they play in society. Diversity and inclusion encompass a wide range of dimensions, including researchers' demographics, epistemic diversity and stakeholder engagement¹. We aim at fostering the engagement of knowledge systems with societal needs and challenges. This is in line with calls such as the UNESCO recommendations on Open Science for more participation and engagement with societal actors in knowledge generation, benefiting collective well-being and reducing knowledge divides. This is also echoed by the CWTS UNESCO Chair on Diversity and Inclusion in Global Science. In realising our vision, we do not expect to just provide advice based on our research, but also to lead by example, by applying our strategic and operational objectives to ourselves and our most immediate communities (e.g. colleagues, university, societies).

¹ The diversity of stakeholder engagement shapes and enriches knowledge systems, with other non-academic sectors also contributing to knowledge creation, such as industry, NGOs and policy makers, also in interaction with knowledge systems like indigenous or experiential knowledge.

3. Strategic objectives

Our vision is intentionally broad. It forces us to zoom in on strategic objectives that we believe are most relevant in realising this vision. Our two strategic objectives are to:

- A. Understand and enable diversity for open and connected knowledge systems; and
- B. Understand and strengthen the engagement between science, society and the environment to address complex challenges.

A. Understand and enable diversity for open and connected knowledge systems

Diversity and inclusion are essential elements of thriving knowledge systems, encompassing demographic and epistemic diversity, diversity in research practices, institutions and organisations, and in the actors and communities that participate in knowledge production and use.

CWTS is a key actor providing research analytics and indicators, contributing to shape the broader science landscape (e.g. through the provision of metrics for policy and organizational decision-making). Innovations in open and alternative data infrastructures create new ways to make visible a wider range of knowledge contributions (e.g. data, software, communication, citizen science), helping to value more diverse forms of work and enabling communities to develop more contextual, locally situated indicators. We also study how organisational structures and governance influence who participates in science and which knowledge forms are valued. Moreover, we also focus on participatory forms of research such as transdisciplinarity and citizen science and how these accommodate diverse actors, values, and knowledge practices.

CWTS is well-positioned to study and make visible existing problems of diversity and inclusion, such as epistemic diversity, demographic diversity and academic freedom, supporting academic organisations in reflecting on and strengthening related initiatives. We also aim to support non-academic organisations, such as industry, NGOs, and policymakers, in connecting and engaging with science, thereby fostering the open and connected knowledge systems central to our vision.

B. Understand and strengthen the engagement between science, society and the environment to address complex challenges

Many societal and environmental challenges, such as climate change, sustainability, pollution, or polarisation are complex and require multidimensional, multidisciplinary, and transdisciplinary approaches involving multiple stakeholders. We aim to study how such challenges are approached within science, identify barriers to these approaches, and develop interventions to promote epistemic diversity.

We contribute to the development of participatory scientific practices to help address complex societal and environmental challenges, considering how societal actors engage in the co-production, dissemination, and use of scientific knowledge. We also analyse how research findings on complex challenges are taken up in politics, especially when policy directions are contested, and in societally and environmentally urgent settings (e.g. sustainability, climate change, political polarisation, critical strategic technologies, etc.). This is pursued not only through research and recommendations but also through teaching (e.g. the bachelor Science for Sustainable Societies - SfSS).

4. Operational objectives

Figure 1. General outline of Strategic Objectives and Operational Objectives for Focal Area Engagement & Inclusion

The operational objectives (OOs) of FA E&I further specify what we aim to achieve through this strategy, providing greater direction and more concrete goals. Each operational objective has a different focus and contributes to strategic objectives A and B to various degrees, as illustrated in Fig. 1. OO1 is transversal, focusing on participatory and multi-perspective approaches, providing methodological and infrastructural support to the other OOs and both strategic objectives. OO2 focuses on inclusion and open governance in academic organisations, OO3 on engagement between actors within knowledge systems, OO4 on engagement and knowledge production in contentious challenges, and OO5 on justice and equity in global science.

OO1. Developing novel, participatory, and multi-perspective approaches for the studying and monitoring of science and its interactions with society.

How science and knowledge systems are monitored directly influences how they understand and improve themselves. Guided by the Dutch axiom *meten is weten* (to measure is to know), this OO departs from the standpoint that the indicators, and frameworks used to study knowledge systems are not neutral, but they shape how they are valued or remain (in-)visible. Grounded in the scientometric tradition

of CWTS and expanding to other disciplinary perspectives, this OO reimagines how science, its actors, and interactions are studied.

Central to this OO is the implementation of the *Multiversatory*, proposed by the UNESCO Chair on Diversity and Inclusion in Global Science, which aims to integrate heterogeneous data sources and multi-perspective approaches in monitoring knowledge systems. Its realisation will encompass federated and democratic data infrastructures alongside new analytics to expand our understanding of how knowledge and innovation systems function (e.g. scientific mobility, funding flows, epistemic inequalities, science-society interactions, etc.) Attention will also be paid to technological challenges, such as AI, that risk introducing new biases and opacity into science systems. Participatory approaches are central, empowering communities to become active co-producers of knowledge and monitoring systems. This OO will provide methodological and infrastructural support for the broader FA E&I, enabling more diverse, inclusive, and epistemically rich representations of science and knowledge, through tools and active engagements with academic, societal, industry, and policy actors.

OO2. Understanding and shaping diversity, inclusion, and open governance in academic organisations.

Academic organisations are complex social environments where values and power structures are ingrained in everyday practices, shaping who participates, whose knowledge is recognised, and how decisions are made. Despite growing attention to diversity and inclusion in the context of *Open Science* and *Reward and Recognition*, persistent inequalities remain related to gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, unequal stakeholder representation, and the marginalisation of diverse epistemologies. Academic culture plays a role in enabling or constraining inclusion, determining which career trajectories are considered legitimate, what forms of knowledge and outputs are valued, and how institutions are organised. This OO focuses on how diversity, inclusion, and open governance take shape within academic organisations, supporting their transformation towards more equitable and openly governed systems.

We aim to understand how institutional governance shapes transparency, participation, and accountability in academic decision-making, paying attention to how reward and recognition systems signal which contributions are valued and whether they reinforce or challenge existing inequalities. We also reflect on emerging developments, such as the use of AI in academic evaluation, which may reshape organisational practices and reinforce existing biases. We consider the roles and perspectives of a wide range of actors within and around academia,

recognising that more inclusive academic systems require broader forms of representation and engagement.

OO3. Understanding, mapping and promoting interactions and engagement between different actors within knowledge systems.

Knowledge systems are shaped by the interactions between diverse actors, whose collaboration, communication, and engagement determine how knowledge is incorporated in society. This OO focuses on understanding, mapping, and enhancing engagement among academia, policymakers, industry, NGOs, and citizens. We will pay increasing attention to contexts in the Global South and communities that are often underrepresented or excluded from knowledge processes.

Studying interactions within knowledge systems includes researching transdisciplinary forms of engagement or science-for-policy interfaces; where interactions between researchers, policymakers, and societal actors shape how evidence is communicated, taken up, and used in decision-making; as well as the role of science communication and public engagement in shaping relationships among actors. Furthermore, it entails understanding how innovation and technology developments are embedded in these systems, and how industry and other stakeholders contribute to, and are influenced by, knowledge production and use. Our goal is to understand and strengthen the interactions between science, society, and the environment. We map how actors interact, including questions of how transdisciplinary engagement takes shape across sectors, how communities, policymakers, industry, and scientists connect and exchange knowledge, and how science communication and public engagement influence these dynamics.

OO4. Understanding and improving engagement and knowledge production and use around contentious societal and environmental challenges.

Complex challenges involving technoscientific knowledge often generate disagreement among actors over both problems and solutions. Climate change is a prime example of societal contention related to technoscientific knowledge, where solutions are contested (e.g. climate mitigation vs. climate adaptation), and where the vested interests of various actors, including industry, play a role. In other cases, grassroots initiatives emerge, with citizens taking to the streets, demanding climate action and encouraging researchers to help address these issues.

The politicisation of science, driven by factors like the rise of populist critiques, misalignments between research and economic values, underrepresentation of social groups, and conflicts of interest, undermines the trust in science, while at the same time, there is strong societal demand for knowledge to inform policy. The increasing interaction between science and society is expected to be beneficial for both, moving away from the classical *ivory tower* position of academia. However, it remains an open question how to make these interactions and dialogues more fruitful, while avoiding its potential drawbacks.

In this OO we wish to better understand the role that science plays in societal contention. We study how scientific knowledge operates within contentious contexts, including how scientists address complex challenges, how societal contention shapes trust, as well as how misinformation fuels critique and contestation. We also examine how politics and (social) media interact with science in such settings. Our objective is not only to study these dynamics, but also to provide advice on how science can help address contentious issues, including how to prevent science from becoming a divisive force and how it may contribute to their resolution.

OO5. Studying and advancing justice and equity in global science.

Global science is deeply influenced by geography, power, and history, making justice and equity critical concerns in how knowledge is produced and whose priorities it serves. This OO focuses on the structural conditions shaping justice and equity in global science, including how collaborations, funding flows, mobility, and (in)access to global academic infrastructures systematically (dis)advantage different actors. Particular attention is given to colonial legacies and practices such as helicopter science. Attention to the Global South, understood as a vast and diverse environment of multiple knowledge systems, will be central, in alignment with the UNESCO Chair on Diversity and Inclusion in Global Science.

A distinctive focal point is science diplomacy, the practices through which scientific knowledge interact with foreign policy, international relations, and global governance. This includes the everyday interactions of researchers and societal actors who shape how knowledge travels across communities and contributes to collective decision-making. We will study how academic careers and funding schemes determine who participates in science diplomacy, how power relations shape the inclusion or exclusion of certain regions, communities, and traditions in global knowledge production, how broader involvement of societal actors (e.g. NGOs, indigenous communities) can strengthen the democratic quality of science-

based global governance, and how stronger evidence-based forms of science diplomacy can be supported.